

FRACTURE MECHANISM OF GLASS CLOTH/EPOXY LAMINATES IN
FRACTURE TOUGHNESS TESTS AT LIQUID NITROGEN
TEMPERATURE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a fracture mechanism of plain woven glass cloth/epoxy laminates in a compact tension specimen at liquid nitrogen temperature. Comparisons were also made between the CT specimens at 296K and 77K. The micro-fracture behaviors were investigated by surface observations in the vicinity of a notch root using an optical microscope. It was found that the fracture toughness J_{max} at 77K was 3.3 times as large as one at 296K, and that the former values varied widely. Tensile tests of the constituents of the GFRP revealed that these characteristics of the GFRP were primarily attributed to that of the glass fiber. Through the microscopic and fractographic observations, the growth processes of micro-crackings in the matrix were clarified at each temperature. The fracture mechanism that the fracture toughness of the GFRP specimen was increased at 77K is discussed.

KEY WORDS: GFRP; Fracture toughness; Compact tension specimen; J-integral;
Cryogenic temperature.

1. INTRODUCTION

With advance of the superconductivity technology, GFRP laminates are one of the most promising materials for use as structural supporting member, since GFRP meets electrical insulation performance and those mechanical properties are elevated at a low temperature. On the other hand, fiber reinforced composites including GFRP are often used in satellites for structural components owing to its high specific strength and stiffness.

Some reviews have been published⁽¹⁾⁻⁽³⁾ that look at these conditions, and several studies reported on the fracture of GFRP laminates at liquid nitrogen temperature or liquid helium one^{(4),(5)}. O.Takaai et. al studied the strength of GFRP specimens from the law of mixture at low temperature⁽⁶⁾, and then investigated the fracture behavior of notched GFRP specimens applying linear fracture mechanics⁽⁷⁾. N.Nishijima et. al reported fracture process of GFRP laminates at cryogenic temperature using an AE method⁽⁸⁾. However, there has not been much research on microscopic deformation and fracture mechanism of GFRP⁽⁹⁾.

In this paper, fracture toughness tests of glass cloth/epoxy laminates were carried out at liquid nitrogen temperature (77K) using CT specimens and compared with the results at room temperature (296K). Load vs. crack opening displacement curves were obtained at each temperature. Correspondence between the load–displacement curves and the damage zones was clarified. Furthermore, microscopic observation ahead of the pre–crack tip was performed in order to clarify the fracture mechanism at 77K.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

2.1 Specimen The materials used in this study were glass cloth/epoxy laminates which were composed of epoxy resin as the matrix and plain woven glass cloth as the reinforcement. The laminates were fabricated by the hand lay–up method in our laboratory. The laminates consisted of 24 plies giving them a thickness of 5 mm. The fiber volume fraction was about $40\pm 2\%$. The mechanical properties of the laminates are shown in Table 1. Specimens were soaked in the liquid nitrogen directly so that tensile tests and fracture toughness tests at 77K could be performed. Regarding the simplicity of chucking the specimen into such an environment, it was preferable that any specimen be loaded by means of pin loading. So we selected the specimen configuration shown in Figure 1. The reinforcement direction of the glass cloth coincided with the loading direction and the transverse one. The specimen geometries and dimensions are shown in the figure.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of GFRP laminates

Specimen(Temp.)	σ_B , MPa	ϵ_B , %	E, GPa
GFRP(296K)	3.22×10^2	1.88	19.5
GFRP(77K)	5.57	–	23.1

2.2 Experimental method The test specimen employed to determine the fracture toughness was the compact tension (CT) specimen. The load–line crack opening displacement (COD)

FIGURE 1. Sizes and dimensions of specimens

between the knife edges was monitored using a double cantilever type clip gage during the test. In general, we sometimes encounter buckling failure mode in fracture toughness tests of advanced composite materials using CT specimens, since the tensile strength and the compressive one are different. Although it is necessary for the CT specimen to avoid the compressive failure, in the present study it was found that the specimens did not fracture in the buckling mode at any temperature.

The specimens were tested on a Shimadzu Autograph testing machine with a definite crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min at room temperature (296K) and liquid nitrogen temperature (77K).

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Stress-strain curve There have been some studies on the improvement of the strength in GFRP laminates at 77K. In the present study, to verify the variation of the basic mechanical properties, tensile tests of the dog-bone type specimen designed not to be broken by pin-loading were performed at 77K, and then these results were compared with the ones

at 296K. The typical stress-strain curves of GFRP laminates is shown in Figure 2.

At 77K, it was confirmed that the specimen was deformed over the measurable limit of the

FIGURE 2. Typical stress-strain curves

FIGURE 3. Photographs showing fractured tensile specimens

strain gage (about 2%). After this measurable limit of the strain gage used at the low temperature, displacement between the upper and the lower pin was switched to monitor instead of the strain gage output. It was found that the load–displacement relation was linear up to the breaking point of the specimen. The stress–strain curve was obtained by extrapolation shown as the dotted line in the figure. Thus, it was learned that the stress–strain relation is also linear.

Compared with the results at 296K, it was found that the breaking stress and strain at 77K increased about 1.6 times and double on average, respectively. Photographs of the fractured specimen are shown in the Figure 3 where a lot of interlaminar fractures which occurred in the specimen at 77K can be seen. Knee points could be laid on the stress–strain curves at both temperatures which were regarded as the initiation point of debonding between the weft and the matrix. At the lower temperature, it was seen that the knee–point stress increased and that the profile of the stress–strain curve near the knee point were different. Furthermore, it was found that the elastic modulus of GFRP increased at 77K, but that the secondary elastic modulus remained almost the same. The primary elastic modulus depends upon the improvement of the resin's elastic modulus. On the other hand, after the knee point, the secondary elastic modulus is not affected by the matrix owing to the occurrence of interfacial debonding. If the elastic modulus of the fiber remained unchanged, it must be considered that the secondary elastic modulus also remained the same.

3.2 *Fracture toughness tests* Typical load vs. crack opening displacement curves obtained from the fracture toughness tests using the CT specimens are shown in Figure 4.

FIGURE 4. Typical load vs. crack opening displacement curves

Obviously, it was found that the maximum load and the crack opening displacement at the

maximum load point at 77K were larger than those obtained at 296K. In the case of 77K, the load declined differently after the maximum load point compared to the one at 296K. The distinctive feature of the load–displacement curve at 77K was that the load declined stepwise as shown in the Figure 4. The fracture toughness of the GFRP laminates was evaluated in terms of the J–integral. It is questionable whether the non–linear fracture mechanics parameter is suitable for evaluating the fracture toughness of the GFRP. As our main purpose is to examine the fracture mechanism at different temperatures, the J–integral is adopted as the primary estimation for the fracture toughness. The J–integral values were calculated from the formula proposed in the JSME S–001⁽¹⁰⁾. The relation between the fracture toughness values at both temperatures and the crack opening displacements at maximum load points are shown in Figure 5.

FIGURE 5. Relation between fracture toughness value and crack opening displacement at maximum loading point

This relation revealed that the fracture toughness values at 77K (J_{max}) were about 3.3 times as large as those at 296K. Furthermore, on the lower temperature side not only the J_{max} values but also the crack opening displacements varied widely. This can be attributed to the fact that microscopic fracture mechanisms up to the maximum load point were different. Figure 6 shows the spread of the damage zone after the maximum load point. On the lower temperature side, the dimension of the damage zone along the load line was larger compared with that of the one at room temperature. In addition, the characteristics of the fractures inside

the damage zones differed. Although numerous micro-cracks were observed regularly between the interfaces in the case of 296K, it was found that the size as well as the spatial location of the micro-cracks were different in the case of 77K. The final damage zone area at 77K is larger than that at 296K as shown in Figure 6.

FIGURE 6. Macroscopic view of damage zone after maximum load point

FIGURE 7. Comparison of damage-zone sizes at same load level

However, the damage zone areas at 296K were larger compared with each other at the same load level (Figure 7). From the experimental fact that the knee-point stress increased at 77K, this can be attributed to the improvement of the apparent initiation stress in interfacial debonding. Therefore, at the same load level, the size of the damage zone at 77K was seen to be smaller, since the damage zone was formed with the interfacial debondings or micro-cracks of the matrix.

3.3 Tensile tests of constituents of the GFRP Tensile tests of glass roving fiber and epoxy resin which were the constituents of the GFRP were carried out. As the preparation of the tensile specimen of the glass roving fiber, one fiber bundle was pulled out of the glass cloth used in this experiment, and then it was fixed to the GFRP tab by an adhesive. On the other hand, the tensile specimen of the resin was machined into the specimen geometry shown in the Figure 1 as well as the laminates.

At 77K, it was found that the breaking load or the breaking stress of both specimens increased (Table 2). The breaking load of the glass roving fiber was about 2.2 times and the breaking stress of the epoxy resin was about 1.4 times as large as those at 296K. So the improvement of the mechanical property of the glass fiber was remarkable compared to that of the resin. From these experimental results, it was felt that the improvement of the strength and/or the fracture toughness value in the GFRP laminates depended upon the mechanical characteristics of the glass fiber at the lower temperature. Concerning the characteristics of the fracture of the glass fiber, it is important that not only the breaking load but also the breaking displacement increased at the lower temperature. To obtain the fracture strain of the glass fiber directly was so difficult. In this experiment, some specimens which had a different gage length were tested in tension to obtain the true breaking displacement by revising the compliances of the load-displacement curve. As for the results, it was ascertained that the breaking displacement of the glass roving fiber increased. So, this is attributed to the improvement of the fracture toughness in the CT specimen.

Table 2 Variation of mechanical properties of constituents

Constituents	296K	77K
Glass roving fiber P_B , N	34.9	79.3
Epoxy resin σ_B , Mpa	57.7	78.7

3.4 Discussion of fracture mechanism In order to reveal the fracture mechanism of the

GFRP specimen with a notch at a microscopic level, the damage zone ahead of the notch was observed using a metallurgical microscope. At 77K, numerous micro-cracks (mainly, matrix cracking) were found which occurred at the matrix part. Although, at 296K, the damage zone could be observed as a whitening zone at a macroscopic level, there was no interfacial debonding and/or matrix cracking at the microscopic level. Photographs taken at the maximum load points representing the microscopic damage are shown in Figure 8. There are numerous micro-cracks surrounding the mechanical notch at 77K. These micro-cracks connected with each other evading the fiber bundle in front, and then joined to become a major crack. On the other hand, at 296K, the interfacial debondings which accounted for the micro-cracks just mentioned grew taking the shortest path of the ligament. According to variation of the relative relation between the brittleness of the resin and the interfacial strength or the glass roving's strength, such a formation mechanism of the damage was obtained. Further, a different crack-propagating path was observed. The occurrence of the numerous

FIGURE 8. Microscopic surface observation in the vicinity of pre-crack tip

micro-cracks at the low temperature blunts the crack, and it is considered to be one of the main factors in the improvement of the fracture toughness.

4. CONCLUSION

Fracture toughness tests and tensile tests of glass cloth/epoxy laminates were carried out at 77K and 296K. The fracture mechanism of the CT specimen was discussed in view of the microscopic surface observation and the tensile tests of the constituents. The results obtained are as follows :

- (1) Both the breaking stress and the fracture toughness value of the GFRP specimens increased at the lower temperature, respectively.
- (2) The damage zone size of the CT specimen at the maximum load point became larger as the temperature decreased. It was found that the size and the spatial distance of the micro-cracks which composed the damage were macroscopically larger at 77K.
- (3) The tensile tests of the constituents revealed that the breaking load of the glass roving fiber at 77K was about 2.3 times as large as the one at 296K, remaining the elastic modulus constant, but that the epoxy resin showed more brittleness as temperature decreased. It was found that the improvement of the fracture toughness at 77K mainly depended upon the mechanical characteristics of the glass fiber.
- (4) The enlargement of the damage zone size in the CT specimen improved the fracture toughness at the lower temperature. This enlargement was caused by the fact that the ratio of the interfacial strength to the glass fiber decreased.
- (5) From the above experimental results obtained, the fracture mechanism of the GFRP specimen, which increased at the lower temperature, was clarified.

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